

From the Editor

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18096897

Dear Members of the Academic Community,

This issue of the *Journal of Culture, Society and Communication*, which approaches the disciplines of culture, society, and communication from a holistic perspective, aims to contribute to the academic field across a broad spectrum ranging from digital media ecosystems to traditional cultural heritage, from dynamics of addiction to the transformation of public relations. As a peer-reviewed scholarly platform, our journal publishes studies that examine cultural production, social interactions, and communication practices in both global and local contexts. The four works included in this issue further reinforce this mission. Our second issue consists of three research articles and one book review.

The first article, Şule Yüksel Özmen's "Fan Journalism on YouTube: The Case of BTS Fandom," addresses fan journalism in digital media environments as an alternative form of cultural production. Drawing on cultural studies, media convergence, and participatory culture theories, the study conceptualizes fan journalism as a hybrid practice combining amateur creativity with professional journalistic norms, grounded in Henry Jenkins's concepts of participatory culture and remix practices. By emphasizing the increasingly significant role of fan dynamics in communication studies, this article makes an important contribution

to the field of cultural communication.

The second article, "Evaluation of Primary School Students' Internet Addiction Based on Parents' Opinions, Control, and Guidance" by Alper Şimşek and Zekiye Kahraman, examines internet addiction among primary school students within the context of parental characteristics. Based on a relational survey model, the study draws on data collected from the parents of 150 fourth-grade students at a public school. The data, obtained through the Parent-Child Internet Addiction Scale and a personal information form, were analyzed using non-parametric statistical methods. Within the scope of society and communication studies, this research sheds light on the effects of digital technologies on family dynamics, emphasizes the preventive role of parental interventions, and offers empirically grounded recommendations for educational policies.

The third article, "An Evaluation of the Erzincan Cengerli Kilim as a Geographical Indication and Cultural Asset" by Neslihan İter and Necibe Şen, evaluates traditional handicrafts in the context of cultural heritage and economic sustainability. Emphasizing the need to preserve handicrafts that have historically functioned as a silent language, the study focuses on the nearly forgotten Cengerli kilim of the Refahiye district in Erzincan.

Employing qualitative methods, the researchers conducted fieldwork in the production village and collected data through face-to-face interviews with two local individuals knowledgeable about this craft. The kilim's distinctive feature is that one short edge is finished through weaving, while the opposite edge is tied using the macramé technique and left fringed. By presenting a concrete example of the preservation and economic valorization of local heritage, this article discusses the contribution of cultural values in disadvantaged regions to social sustainability within the field of cultural studies.

The final work, a book review titled “Public Relations in Digital Transformation: An Analysis of Yeşim Güçdemir’s Work” by Nergiz Akar, examines Yeşim Güçdemir’s 2024 book *Digital Transformation and Public Relations*. Güçdemir’s work addresses digitalization in the context of public relations and provides a comprehensive account of how digital transformation has permanently influenced communication and social relations.

We look forward to receiving your scholarly contributions for Volume 2, Issue 3, to be published in the first half of 2026.

Stay with truth and science.

Dr. Aytaç Burak DERELİ
JCSC / Publisher and Editor-in-Chief

